

Local Government in Canada

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Canada: An Introduction

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Local Responsibilities and the Challenge of Local Government Capacity

Local governments in Canada have responsibility first and foremost for local physical services, such as planning and development permits, water and wastewater, roads and transit, and parks.³¹ But many are also responsible for a variety of other services, including economic development initiatives, emergency services and police and (especially in Ontario) local administration of provincially funded social services and social housing. Beyond this, community demand often pushes local governments to fund services in fields well beyond their core mandate – such as arts and culture and immigrant settlement initiatives.

While both rural and urban municipalities in Canada deliver a range of services, service needs and demands vary across these two contexts. In urban municipalities – especially those which experience rapid growth – distinctly urban infrastructure such as transit, public space and (in some places) affordable housing loom large. Local police and emergency services are big-ticket items in many urban municipalities, and some also increasingly embrace broader ‘place-based policy’ roles that include elements such as support for the arts, partnerships with higher education institutions, and/or support for the needs of new immigrants. In rural areas, by contrast, the focus tends to be on maintaining basic services in a low-density context where per-capita infrastructure costs are high,³² pressing needs include attracting economic development in the face of decline,³³ supporting an aging population, and improving internet connectivity.³⁴

As might be expected, capacity to deliver services is limited in multiple ways in small rural municipalities. Roughly 60 per cent of Canadian municipalities have five staff members or less,³⁵ so limited administrative resources are a major issue. Fiscally, not only do small

³¹ See the report section 1 on the System of Local Government in Canada for details.

³² The maintenance of local rural roads alone consumes 25% or more of many rural municipal budgets.

³³ As one respondent to interviews for the project noted, the oft-cited story of ‘decline’ is actually a complicated one in the Canadian context. On the one hand, many ‘traditional’ rural economic sectors do continue to decline in terms of output; on the other hand, rural areas as discussed in detail in report section 1 on the System of Local Government in Canada, an out-migration of affluent homeowners from urban areas, accelerated by the Covid-19 pandemic, is bringing new money into some rural areas, but it is not clear to what extent these trends will affect rural economic prospects.

³⁴ See, for example, Federation of Canadian Municipalities, ‘Rural Challenges, National Opportunity: Shaping the Future of Rural Canada’ (2019).

³⁵ *ibid* 9.

municipalities have a smaller local tax base, but in many cases local property values (especially for commercial properties) are stagnant or declining in economically disadvantaged rural areas, which significantly limits fiscal capacity, since local governments across the country are heavily reliant on property taxes for revenue.

While urban municipalities in Canada do not face the same size-related capacity limitations as rural ones, the capacity of urban municipalities to deliver services is nonetheless challenged in a couple of important ways. First, given their heavy reliance on property taxes and their limited jurisdictional autonomy from provincial governments,³⁶ local governments in big cities often face fiscal and jurisdictional limits in responding to emerging concerns in complex policy fields such as infrastructure, immigrant integration, and housing affordability. Effective service provision in such fields often necessitates some form of multilevel collaboration among levels of government, which has historically been difficult to sustain. Second, while in some large urban areas a single municipality covers all or most of the urban region, Canada's three largest city-regions (Toronto, Montreal and Vancouver) are all fragmented among multiple local government units, raising challenges of horizontal coordination in service provision on regional issues.

Responding to Capacity Constraints

Historically, provincial governments have dealt with rural capacity limitations in three main ways. First, in several provinces, some rural areas have no local government, and are administered directly by provincial governments. This has become decreasingly common over time, and as of today, the only province where a large proportion of the population lives in such areas is New Brunswick.³⁷ Second, in many provinces – including the four largest provinces of Ontario, Quebec, Alberta and British Columbia – there has long been an upper tier of local government that provides certain services on a larger geographical scale.³⁸ Finally, some provincial governments (most notably Ontario's) have repeatedly amalgamated small rural municipalities into larger ones. In addition, rural local governments themselves have long engaged in various forms of voluntary inter-municipal service sharing. An innovative recent example comes from Ontario, where regional associations of rural municipalities in two areas

³⁶ See report section 1 on the System of Local Government in Canada.

³⁷ About 30% of the total provincial population of 800,000 lives in areas with no local government. See Michael McKendry, 'Improving the Regional Service Commissions in New Brunswick: Final Report' (Government of New Brunswick 2017). The obvious resulting 'democratic deficit' has led to repeated efforts to develop local government for these parts of New Brunswick, with a new round of consultation on the matter currently underway in 2021.

³⁸ The British Columbia case is unique. The upper tier-units there, designed by the provincial government in the 1960s, are called 'regional districts'. They do not have municipal status, but rather, they are institutional shells that local municipalities can use to share delivery of whatever services they agree to share. See David Cashback, *Regional District Governance in British Columbia: A Case Study in Aggregation* (Institute on Governance 2001).

of the province have organized initiatives to develop broadband internet infrastructure for their communities.³⁹

The limited capacity of urban local governments to deal with complex urban problems became more politically salient in Canada in the early 2000s. Large urban municipalities, facing a fiscal squeeze after a steep decline in intergovernmental transfers in the 1980s and 90s, began to lobby other levels of government for funding assistance. At the same time, large urban areas were becoming increasingly electorally important at both the provincial and federal levels. The result has been the emergence, over the past 15 years, of a variety of multilevel coordination efforts in urban services – ranging from trilevel funding for infrastructure to funding and policy supports for affordable housing and immigrant integration. A significant Canadian literature on multilevel governance and place-based urban policy documents the rise of these initiatives.⁴⁰ The problem of horizontal metropolitan coordination has been addressed in very different ways in Canada's three largest urban areas. In Vancouver, a long-standing collaborative regional government (Metro Vancouver, until recently the Greater Vancouver Regional District) has promoted a shared approach to planning and development issues; in Montreal, a complex system of up to four levels of local government has emerged in response to the social and political heterogeneity of the city-region; and in Toronto, the provincial government has compensated for a lack of regional governing institutions by assuming direct control over large-scale regional development planning and infrastructure since 2005.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Bradford N, 'A National Urban Policy for Canada? The Implicit Federal Agenda' (IRPP Insight no 24, Institute for Research on Public Policy 2018)

Cashaback D, *Regional District Governance in British Columbia: A Case Study in Aggregation* (Institute on Governance 2001)

Horak M and Young R (eds), *Sites of Governance: Multilevel Governance and Policy Making in Canada's Big Cities* (McGill-Queen's University Press 2012)

Federation of Canadian Municipalities, 'Rural Challenges, National Opportunity: Shaping the Future of Rural Canada' (2019)

³⁹ The associations are the Eastern Ontario Wardens' Caucus and the Western Ontario Wardens' Caucus. Details of these two projects can be found at <<https://www.eorn.ca/en/index.aspx>> and <<https://swiftruralbroadband.ca/>>.

⁴⁰ See, for example, Martin Horak and Robert Young (eds), *Sites of Governance: Multilevel Governance and Policy Making in Canada's Big Cities* (McGill-Queen's University Press 2012); Neil Bradford, 'A National Urban Policy for Canada? The Implicit Federal Agenda' (IRPP Insight no 24, Institute for Research on Public Policy 2018).

McKendy M, 'Improving the Regional Service Commissions in New Brunswick: Final Report' (Government of New Brunswick 2017)

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